

Synthesis and characterization of transition metal complexes of a 16-membered (N₄) macrocycle with tetrapeptide features

A. K. Panda*, A. Panda, S. Sutar^a, P. Mishra, S. Pradhan, S. Ghosh and S. Pany

School of Chemistry, Sambalpur University, Jyoti Vihar-768 019, Orissa, India

^aGovernment Autonomous College, Rourkela-769 004, Orissa, India

Manuscript received 18 August 2008, revised 27 April 2009, accepted 18 May 2009

Abstract : A series of macrocyclic complexes of the titled ligand, [16]1,5,6,8,9,13,14,16-octaaza-2,4,10,12-tetraoxo-cyclo decahexane (OTCH) with cobalt(II), nickel(II) and copper(II) have been prepared by the action of formaldehyde on the respective bis(1,5-diamino-1,5-diaza-2,4-dioxopentane) metal complexes. The coordination template effect governs the steric course of the reaction. The structure of the complexes has been elucidated on the basis of IR, electronic and ESR spectral data, magnetic properties and electrochemical studies. All the complexes except copper(II) give two well defined reduction steps corresponding to the formation of a species where the metal can be formally assigned to an oxidation state of +1 and zero. Copper(II) complexes show one reduction step corresponding to zero oxidation state.

Keywords : Tetrapeptide, macrocycle, complex, synthesis.

Introduction

Cyclisation of precursor complexes involving the vicinal amino groups with ketones and CS₂ have been reported¹⁻⁴. In continuation of our earlier work^{5,6} we report the synthesis and characterization of a series of 16-member octaaza 6 : 6 : 6 : 6 annulated macrocyclic complexes involving the template reaction of the corresponding complexes of 1,5-diamino-1,5-diaza-2,4-dioxopentane with formaldehyde.

Experimental

Synthesis of the complexes :

All the chemicals used were of either Glaxo or E. Merck grade. Solvents and metal salts were used without further purification. All the complexes were prepared by an identical method as exemplified below for [Ni(OTCH)(H₂O)₂]Cl₂.

The precursor complex⁴, bis(1,5-diamino-1,5-diaza-2,4-dioxopentane) nickel(II) chloride (0.429 g, 1 mmol) was suspended in 30–50 ml of acetonitrile and maintained 40 °C. It was treated with (1.8 g, 2 mmol) aqueous (37%) formaldehyde. Care was taken for the dropwise addition of formaldehyde with continuous and vigorous stirring

because bulk addition of it results in a gummy product with unknown composition. After about 30–45 min the solids pass into solution with a change in colour from sky blue to pale yellow. In order to catalyze the rate of the reaction, a drop of perchloric acid was added. The resulting solution was reduced to half its volume after stirring for 2 h. The concentrated solution was filtered and treated with a chilled solution of *n*-butanol and ether (1 : 1). A yellow crystalline product was isolated. It was filtered, washed with ether and dried in vacuum. The analytical data of the complexes are recorded in Table 1.

Analysis and measurements :

The metal contents of all complexes were determined by standard methods⁷. Nitrogen was determined by Kjeldhal's method. Carbon and hydrogen were determined with a VEB Laborgerate MLW-CHN micro analyzer. The reflectance and IR spectra of the complexes were recorded on Cary 2390 and Perkin-Elmer 389 spectrophotometers, respectively. The ESR spectra of the copper(II) complexes were recorded as powdered sample (polycrystalline) on a Varian E-112 EPR spectrophotometer with the field set at 3200 G, scan range 2.0 × 1 KG, modulation frequency 100 KHz, microwave frequency 9.44 GHz, re-

Table 1. Analytical data of the metal(II) complexes of OTCH

Complexes (Colour) Exp. formula	Mol. wt. Found (Calcd.)	μ_{eff} (B.M.)	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)					Molar conductance ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)
			M	C	H	N*	X**	
[Co(OTCH)(H ₂ O) ₂] ₂ Cl ₂ (Dark brown)	450 (453)	4.85	12.75 (12.81)	21.00 (21.19)	4.35 (4.42)	30.85 (30.91)	15.71 (15.67)	155
C ₈ H ₂₀ O ₆ N ₈ Cl ₂ Co [Co(OTCH)(H ₂ O) ₂] ₂ Br ₂ (Orange brown)	545 (542)	4.90	10.72 (10.72)	17.54 (17.17)	3.72 (3.69)	25.95 (25.83)	29.48 (29.52)	140
C ₈ H ₂₀ O ₆ N ₈ Br ₂ Co [Co(OTCH)(H ₂ O) ₂](NO ₃) ₂ (Reddish brown)	500 (506)	4.94	11.52 (11.46)	18.90 (18.97)	3.86 (3.95)	27.58 (27.67)	-	133
C ₈ H ₂₀ O ₆ N ₁₀ Co [Ni(OTCH)(H ₂ O) ₂] ₂ Cl ₂ (Pale yellow)	455 (454)	3.15	12.80 (12.49)	21.10 (21.15)	4.37 (4.41)	30.72 (30.84)	15.72 (15.64)	160
C ₈ H ₂₀ O ₆ N ₈ Cl ₂ Ni [Ni(OTCH)(H ₂ O) ₂] ₂ Br ₂ (Yellow)	540 (543)	3.20	10.85 (10.87)	17.75 (17.68)	3.52 (3.68)	25.51 (25.68)	29.40 (29.47)	157
C ₈ H ₂₀ O ₆ N ₈ Br ₂ Ni [Ni(OTCH)(H ₂ O) ₂](NO ₃) ₂ (Yellowish brown)	510 (507)	3.18	11.60 (11.64)	18.97 (18.93)	3.84 (3.94)	27.52 (27.95)	-	140
C ₈ H ₂₀ O ₁₂ N ₁₀ Ni [Cu(OTCH)(H ₂ O) ₂] ₂ Cl ₂ (Dirty green)	460 (458.5)	13.90 (13.85)	20.82 (20.94)	4.30 (4.36)	30.45 (30.53)	15.52 (15.49)	-	162
C ₈ H ₂₀ O ₆ N ₈ Cl ₂ Cu [Cu(OTCH)(H ₂ O) ₂] ₂ Br ₂ (Olive green)	545 (547.5)	11.72 (11.60)	17.45 (17.53)	3.85 (3.65)	25.50 (25.57)	29.35 (29.22)	-	159
C ₈ H ₂₀ O ₆ N ₈ Br ₂ Cu [Cu(OTCH)(H ₂ O) ₂](NO ₃) ₂ (Bottle green)	508 (511.5)	12.32 (12.41)	18.68 (18.77)	3.95 (3.91)	27.42 (27.37)	-	-	142
C ₈ H ₂₀ O ₆ N ₁₀ Cu								

ceiver gain 10×10^2 and modulation amplitude 0.63×10 G. The conductivities of the complexes in dioxan were measured with a Systronics conductivity bridge. The room temperature magnetic moment values were determined by Gouy's method using Hg[Co(SCN)₄] as calibrant. Electrochemical studies were made with a Systronic polarograph type 1632 in 80% DMF with KClO₄ as the supporting electrolyte. X-Ray diffraction data were collected on a Philips PW 1710 diffractometer equipped with a Philips PW 1830 X-ray generator using CuK α radiation and a graphic monochromator. Powdered samples were scanned with a scanning rate of 1 degree per minute. The analysis of X-ray diffraction data was carried out using

LSUCRIPC software (Courtesy R. Garvey, North Dakota University, USA, through Dr. B. S. Acharya, RRL, Bhubaneswar) using an IBM compatible PC-AT (80486, 66 MHz).

Results and discussion

The complexes are highly stable with melting points >250 °C, above which the complexes slowly start to decompose. These are slowly attacked by dilute acids and alkalis. The complexes in dioxan/DMF solution have high molar conductance values suggesting them to be 1 : 2 electrolytes. The vicinal amino groups of the precursor complexes are in suitable orientations to undergo Schiff

base condensation reaction with formaldehyde to yield octaaza (N_8) macrocyclic complexes as represented below (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1

Formation of 6 : 6 : 6 : 6 annular macrocyclic complexes is evident from their analytical data (Table 1) and other physico-chemical studies.

IR spectral studies :

The IR spectra of the macrocyclic complexes have been compared with the precursor complexes of 1,5-diamino-1,5-diaza-2,4-dioxopentane (DDDP) and other related complexes. The ligand moiety in these complexes have been expected to exist in different keto-enol and amidimidol tautomeric forms including hydrogen bonding.

A broad band with a centre of gravity $\sim 3480\text{ cm}^{-1}$ has been observed which is due to the combined mode of ν_{NH} , ν_{OH} and coordinated H_2O molecules. The disappearance of the precursor bands at $\sim 1665\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and 1120 cm^{-1} due to $\delta(\text{NH}_2)$ and $\rho_r(\text{NH}_2)$ suggest that the reaction involving the vicinal amino groups has taken place⁸.

A multiplet at $\sim 3240, 3200, 3195\text{ cm}^{-1}$ probably arises due to ν_{NH} in different chemical environment⁹⁻¹¹ and a doublet at ~ 1275 and 1150 cm^{-1} , due to wagging vibration of coordinated and free secondary NH group¹² are observed. An increase in the absorption frequency and also intensity of δCH_2 at ~ 1160 and 815 cm^{-1} , clearly suggest the reaction of formaldehyde with vicinal -NH_2 group of precursor complexes. It also suggests that the -CH_2 group of the macrocycle does not take part in the tautomerism.

The bands due to ν_{CH_2} , $\nu_{\text{C-C}}$, $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$, $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$, $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$, $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{N-N}}$ ¹³ at $\sim 2850, 1630, 1605, 1575, 1435, 1316$ and 1030 cm^{-1} respectively undergo a slight shift in

their position and change in intensity as compared to our earlier observations⁶. The shifting is due to the introduction of a $\text{-CH}_2\text{-}$ group in place of $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$ which affects the electron density in the macrocyclic ligand framework.

A broad band at $\sim 1040\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is tentatively assigned to $\nu(\text{OH})$ and the broadness of this band is probably due to intermolecular hydrogen bonding. Additional bands ~ 755 and 550 cm^{-1} are attributed to $\rho_r(\text{H}_2\text{O})$ and $\rho_w(\text{H}_2\text{O})$ of coordinated water¹⁴. The coordinated nature of the water molecule is further supplemented by the appearance of another band at $\sim 450\text{ cm}^{-1}$ attributed to $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ ¹⁵.

All complexes have high molar conductance value ranging from 165 to $133\ \Omega^{-1}\text{ mol}^{-1}$, like the corresponding precursor molecules. In order to confirm further the nature of the anions (coordinated/free), the spectra of the nitrate complexes were studied. A coordinated nitrate group generally absorbs at ~ 1020 and 1240 cm^{-1} . However no such bands were observed in the nitrate complexes suggesting the non-coordination of the anionic group¹⁶.

Thermal analysis :

The thermograms of the complexes follow the same pattern of thermal decomposition. The complexes remain almost unaffected up to $160\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, which eliminates the possibility of the presence of lattice water^{17,18}. The weight loss at a comparatively higher temperature of $\sim 180^\circ$ corresponds to two water molecules^{19,20} suggesting that they are coordinated in conformity with our earlier observation from IR spectral investigations. The endothermic peaks occurring in the second and third step at 350 and $\sim 490\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, respectively, correspond to the decomposition of organic constituents, leaving behind the respective metal oxides.

Electronic spectra and magnetic properties :

The spectra of cobalt(II) macrocyclic complexes show three bands in the region 8000 to 17000 cm^{-1} and resemble the characteristic spectral features of octahedral geometry. The band near $\sim 8180\text{ cm}^{-1}$ arises due to the transition ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)(\nu_1)$. The broad band in the region $\sim 19000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ arises due to the transition ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ respectively²¹. In these complexes a shoulder is observed near $\sim 15900\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for the ligand field transition ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}$ and a band $\sim 25500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to charge transfer or intra ligand transitions.

The room temperature magnetic moment values of the cobalt(II) complexes lie in the range 4.85–4.94 B.M. (Table 1). The ligand field splitting energy ($10 Dq$), Racah parameter (B , C), ligand field parameters (F_2 , F_4), % of covalency (β^0) and transition ratio (ν_2/ν_1) lie in the range (9120–9353), (835–790, 3867–3661), (1387–1313, 110–105) cm^{-1} , (14.52–19.02)% and (2.13–2.14) for chloride, bromide and nitrate complexes respectively. The values of β^0 and transition ratio are in good agreement with the cobalt(II) complexes in an average O_h environment²².

In the present nickel(II) complexes a tetragonal splitting for the excited ${}^3T_{2g}(F)$ level has been observed. The split components of ${}^3T_{2g}$ are observed at $\sim 9000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and 13950 cm^{-1} due to ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3E_{2g}(\nu_1^a)$ and ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3E_{2g}(\nu_1^b)$ transitions respectively. The relative intensity of former band is higher. The band due to ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(\nu_2)$ and ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(\nu_3)$ transition occur in the high frequency region at $\sim 20000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and 27000 cm^{-1} respectively. The values of the tetragonal parameters D_t , in plane and out of plane field strength D_q^E ($1395\text{--}1430 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and D_q^A ($405\text{--}580 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) have been calculated²³. The room temperature magnetic moment values of these complexes are found within the range 3.15–3.20 B.M. (Table 1) and are in good agreement with pseudo octahedral nickel(II) species.

The ligand field spectra of the copper(II) complexes exhibited a broad envelope in the region $\sim 16500 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. In addition to this a strong CT band at $\sim 24200 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is also observed. The envelope of the former band is characteristic of the ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$ transition for the d^9 configuration of the copper(II) ion in a distorted octahedral geometry. Jahn-Teller distortion expected in d^9 configuration usually disturbs the degeneracy causing a split in the energy level due to a tetragonal distortion in the geometry²⁴. The room temperature magnetic moment values of the present copper(II) complexes (Table 1) ranging from 1.70–1.75 B.M. resemble with the feature of copper(II) ion in a square planar geometry under D_{4h} symmetry.

The ESR spectra of the polycrystalline samples contained two signals corresponding to g_{\parallel} (2.247–2.255) and g_{\perp} (2.047–2.058) due to an anisotropic environment confirming the tetragonal distortion from perfect O_h geo-

metry around the copper(II) ion. The observed $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp} > 2.0$ and $A_{\parallel} > (202\text{--}207) > A_{\perp}$ ($110\text{--}120 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) suggests an axially elongated geometry with $d_{x^2-y^2}$ (or ${}^2B_{1g}$) ground electronic state of the metal ion and a major distortion in copper(II) complexes from O_h symmetry to D_{4h} symmetry⁵. The covalency parameter, α^2 found to be 0.879 which is more than that of the precursor complex⁴. From the ESR spectral data it is suggested that these macrocyclic complexes have less covalent character in bonding involving the metal ion and ligand^{26,27}. Thus the unpaired electron of the copper(II) complexes spends about 13.50% of its time on the ligand nitrogen donor sites.

Electrochemical studies :

The inverse of the slope of the polarograms are in the range 62–82 mV and the high values provide evidence for the irreversible nature of the redox processes.

Cobalt(II) complexes show two diffusion controlled and irreversible reduction waves of almost equal height²⁸. The first wave and second wave reduction potentials of these cobalt(II) complexes are -0.60 V and -0.71 V respectively. High values of $E^1_{1/2}$ and higher height of first wave than precursor complexes suggests the more cathodic nature and first electron, i.e. $\text{Co}^{\text{II}+e} \rightarrow \text{Co}^{\text{I}}$ is more preferable in these complexes than the precursor.

The nickel(II) complexes exhibit two one-electron reduction process in the potential range $\sim -0.4 \text{ V}$ and -1.55 V for the first and second wave reduction potential respectively²⁹. The $E^2_{1/2}$ value for the nickel complexes is more cathodic than the first redox wave.

Copper(II) complexes also exhibit a well defined wave at $E_{1/2}$ value in the range 1.8 V to 2 V vs SCE which is due to quasi-reversible two electron one step reduction process having slope⁻¹ $\sim 72 \text{ mV}$.

X-Ray diffraction studies :

It was observed that the copper(II) complexes are tetragonal whereas nickel(II) and cobalt(II) complexes possesses the crystal class of low symmetry i.e. monoclinic and triclinic respectively^{30,31}. This indicates that the ligand moiety does not effect much in case of copper(II) complexes whereas nickel(II) and cobalt(II) complexes are affected much. The packing of atoms in the unit cell of these complexes are in the order : copper(II) > nickel(II) > cobalt(II) though their ionic radii are nickel(II) > cobalt(II) > copper(II) ions.

It has been observed that the interfacial angle i.e. α , β and γ of present cobalt(II) and nickel(II) complexes are greater than copper(II) complexes. The inter planar distance, d , of these complexes vary to a large extent which indicate the large symmetrical difference of the cobalt(II), nickel(II) and copper(II) complexes.

Conclusion :

Based on the foregoing observations, the following tentative structure (Fig. 2) for the complexes is proposed.

Fig. 2

Acknowledgement

We express our thanks to the Director, Regional Sophisticated Instrumentation Centre, Indian Institute of Technology, Chennai and Indian Institute of Technology, Kharagpur, for recording the IR, reflectance and ESR spectra of the complexes. We are also thankful to Dr. (Mrs.) B. Banerjee, Geological Survey of India, Kolkata for electrochemical studies and discussion.

References

1. A. K. Panda, D. C. Dash, P. Mishra and H. Mohanty, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1997, **36**, 712.
2. A. K. Panda, S. Rout and H. Mohanty, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1994, **33**, 788.
3. K. C. Satpathy, A. K. Panda, D. C. Dash and H. Mohanty, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1994, **33**, 955.
4. K. C. Satpathy, A. K. Panda, A. Naik and S. Chinda, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1994, **71**, 89.
5. K. C. Satpathy, A. K. Panda, R. Mishra, P. Mishra and S. K. Pradhan, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1992, **69**, 119.
6. A. K. Panda, D. C. Dash, A. Panda and P. Mishra, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1998, **37**, 67.
7. A. I. Vogel, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 3rd ed., ELBS and Longmans, Green and Co. Ltd., 1961, pp. 496, 526, 529.
8. C. W. Young and R. B. Duvall, *Anal. Chem.*, 1951, **23**,

- 709.
9. L. J. Bellamy, "The Infrared Spectra of Complex Molecules". Wiley, New York, 1963, 17.
10. C. N. R. Rao, "Chemical Application of Infrared Spectroscopy", Academic Press, New York, 1963.
11. S. M. Peng, G. C. Gordon and V. L. Goedken, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1978, **17**, 119.
12. N. B. Calinip, L. H. Dalg and S. E. Wiberley, "Introduction to Infrared and Raman Spectroscopy", Academic Press, New York, 1975, 321.
13. Z. A. Siddiqui and S. M. Shadab, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2004, **43**, 2274.
14. K. Nakamoto, "Infrared and Raman Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", John Wiley, New York, 3rd ed., 1978, p. 228.
15. H. C. Rai and B. Sahoo, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **53**, 46.
16. H. C. Rai and B. Sahoo, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **53**, 487.
17. A. V. Nikolaev, V. A. Lagvienkl and L. I. Myochina, "Thermal Analysis", Academic Press, New York, 1969, p. 779.
18. P. R. Shukla, V. K. Singh and J. Bhargava, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, **59**, 620.
19. B. Singh, P. L. Maurya, B. V. Agrawal and A. K. Dey, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, **59**, 29.
20. A. K. Panda, S. Rout and H. Mohanty, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1994, **33**, 788.
21. A. B. Lever, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, 204.
22. B. Sahoo and B. K. Mahapatra, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1982, **21**, 376.
23. J. Chakrabarty and B. Sahoo, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1980, **19**, 441.
24. R. W. Hay and B. Jeragh, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1977, 2161.
25. M. Shankar, S. P. Varvey and P. S. Hamee, *Polyhedron*, 1993, **12**, 2775.
26. E. L. Goodman and J. B. Rayner, *Topics in Inorg. Radiochem.*, 1970, **13**, 136.
27. R. S. Drago, "Physical Methods in Inorganic Chemistry", Affiliated East West Press, New Delhi, 1991, 355.
28. F. Larson, G. N. Lamar, B. E. Wagher, J. E. Parks and R. H. Holm, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1972, **11**, 2652.
29. D. P. Fisher, F. C. McElroy and D. J. Macero, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1979, **18**, 2304.
30. A. Abusamleh, P. J. Chemiclewshi, P. R. Warburton, L. Morales, N. A. Stephenson and D. H. Busch, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 1991, **23**, 91.
31. P. A. Padolic, A. J. Jiratamo, N. V. Alcock and D. H. Busch, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1991, **30**, 2713.